

Additional material: Epsilon constraint based QAOA

1 Penalty Operator Expansion

The unconstrained problem is defined as:

$$\min_{x \in \{0,1\}^n} x^\top Q_1 x + \lambda(x^\top Q_2 x - c)^2 \quad (1)$$

The value of the target parameter c depends on the chosen constraint-handling paradigm:

- **Slack Variable Method:** To exactly represent the inequality, integer slack variables are introduced such that $x^\top Q_2 x + \sum_k 2^k s_k = \varepsilon$. This sets the dynamic target to $c = \varepsilon - \sum_k 2^k s_k$, requiring additional auxiliary qubits s_k .
- **Soft Penalty Method (Hess et al.):** The slack variables are omitted to save qubit resources, and the inequality is simply relaxed to an exact equality target, yielding a static $c = \varepsilon$.

Because squaring Objective 2 creates a degree-4 polynomial, Eq. (1) represents a **Higher-Order Unconstrained Binary Optimization (HUBO)** problem. To map this to quantum hardware, we define the corresponding quantum penalty operator H_P :

$$H_P(\lambda, c) = \lambda(H_2 - \hat{c}I)^2 \quad (2)$$

The inclusion of the identity matrix I is mathematically required to translate the classical scalar subtraction into a valid matrix operator. In quantum mechanics, the classical cost of a bitstring x is retrieved via the eigenvalue equation $H_2 |x\rangle = (x^\top Q_2 x) |x\rangle$. To subtract the scalar target c from this eigenvalue, we must apply an operator that leaves the quantum state unchanged while multiplying it by c , which is precisely $(\hat{c}I) |x\rangle = \hat{c} |x\rangle$. Subtracting these two operators yields:

$$(H_2 - \hat{c}I) |x\rangle = H_2 |x\rangle - \hat{c}I |x\rangle = (x^\top Q_2 x - c) |x\rangle \quad (3)$$

Squaring this composite operator accurately reproduces the classical penalty function $(x^\top Q_2 x - c)^2$ as the corresponding eigenvalue.

The total Cost Hamiltonian to be minimized by the QAOA circuit is therefore $H_C = H_1 + H_P$.

Because H_2 is already a quadratic form of Pauli matrices, squaring it in H_P produces three- and four-body interactions. To implement this on quantum hardware, we must explicitly expand and decompose H_P . Let the constraint observable H_2 be defined over the logical qubit indices u and v as:

$$H_2 = \sum_{u=0}^{n-1} h_u Z_u + \sum_{0 \leq u < v < n} J_{uv} Z_u Z_v + c_2 I_n \quad (4)$$

where the coefficients are extracted from the classical matrix Q_2 :

$$J_{uv} = \frac{1}{2} Q_{2,uv}, \quad h_u = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_v Q_{2,uv}, \quad c_2 = \frac{1}{4} \sum_{u,v} Q_{2,uv} + \frac{1}{4} \sum_u Q_{2,uu} \quad (5)$$

1.1 Expansion of the Penalty Operator

To explicitly construct the quantum circuit, we must expand the squared penalty operator:

$$H_P = \lambda(H_2 - cI)^2 = \lambda(A^2 + B^2 + C^2 + 2AB + 2AC + 2BC) \quad (6)$$

We separate the observable H_2 into its logical components:

$$A = \sum_{u=0}^{n-1} h_u Z_u, \quad B = \sum_{0 \leq u < v < n} J_{uv} Z_u Z_v. \quad (7)$$

The identity component C depends entirely on how the target c is defined (with or without slack variables).

First, we expand the terms independent of c . By distributing the products and applying Pauli matrix reduction rules (e.g., $Z_u^2 = I$), we decompose A^2 , B^2 , and $2AB$ into independent k -local elements:

- A^2 (0-local and 2-local terms):

$$A^2 = \sum_{u,v} h_u h_v Z_u Z_v = \left(\sum_u h_u^2 \right) I_n + 2 \sum_{u < v} h_u h_v Z_u Z_v \quad (8)$$

- B^2 (Expansion up to 4-local):

$$\begin{aligned} B^2 &= \sum_{u < v} J_{uv}^2 I_n \\ &+ 2 \sum_{u < v} \left(\sum_{w \neq u,v} J_{uw} J_{vw} \right) Z_u Z_v \\ &+ 2 \sum_{u < v < w < x} (J_{uv} J_{wx} + J_{uw} J_{vx} + J_{ux} J_{vw}) Z_u Z_v Z_w Z_x \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

- $2AB$ (1-local and 3-local terms):

$$2AB = 2 \sum_u \left(\sum_{v \neq u} h_v J_{uv} \right) Z_u + 2 \sum_{u < v < w} (h_u J_{vw} + h_v J_{uw} + h_w J_{uv}) Z_u Z_v Z_w \quad (10)$$

The expansions for C^2 , $2AC$, and $2BC$ depend strictly on the chosen constraint formulation. We analyze both cases below.

1.1.1 Case 1: Slack Free Approach

In the soft penalty method, the target is a static scalar ($c = \varepsilon$). Consequently, C is a purely 0-local identity term: $C = (c_2 - \varepsilon)I_n$. The cross-terms are inherently decomposed without increasing their locality:

$$C^2 = (c_2 - \varepsilon)^2 I_n \quad (11)$$

$$2AC = 2(c_2 - \varepsilon) \sum_u h_u Z_u \quad (12)$$

$$2BC = 2(c_2 - \varepsilon) \sum_{u < v} J_{uv} Z_u Z_v \quad (13)$$

Aggregating all terms, we define the exact sub-Hamiltonians $H_P = H_P^{(0)} + H_P^{(1)} + H_P^{(2)} + H_P^{(3)} + H_P^{(4)}$:

- 0-local:

$$H_P^{(0)} = \lambda \left[\sum_u h_u^2 + \sum_{u < v} J_{uv}^2 + (c_2 - \varepsilon)^2 \right] I_n \quad (14)$$

- 1-local:

$$H_P^{(1)} = 2\lambda \sum_u \left[\sum_{v \neq u} h_v J_{uv} + (c_2 - \varepsilon) h_u \right] Z_u \quad (15)$$

- 2-local:

$$H_P^{(2)} = 2\lambda \sum_{u < v} \left[h_u h_v + (c_2 - \varepsilon) J_{uv} + \sum_{w \neq u, v} J_{uw} J_{vw} \right] Z_u Z_v \quad (16)$$

- 3-local:

$$H_P^{(3)} = 2\lambda \sum_{u < v < w} (h_u J_{vw} + h_v J_{uw} + h_w J_{uv}) Z_u Z_v Z_w \quad (17)$$

- 4-local:

$$H_P^{(4)} = 2\lambda \sum_{u < v < w < x} (J_{uv} J_{wx} + J_{uw} J_{vx} + J_{ux} J_{vw}) Z_u Z_v Z_w Z_x \quad (18)$$

Notice that the higher-order components ($H_P^{(3)}$ and $H_P^{(4)}$) are solely dependent on the classical problem matrix Q_2 and do not depend on the constraint threshold ε .

1.1.2 Case 2: Slack Approach

If the exact inequality is maintained via integer slack variables, the target becomes dynamic: $c = \varepsilon - \sum_k 2^k s_k$. To represent this on quantum hardware, the binary slack variables s_k must be mapped to independent Pauli operators Z_{s_k} acting on an auxiliary register via the transformation $s_k = (I - Z_{s_k})/2$.

By substituting this mapping, the component C ceases to be a scalar and becomes an active 1-local Hamiltonian spanning the slack register:

$$C_{slack} = \tilde{c}I_n - \sum_{k=0}^{M-1} 2^{k-1} Z_{s_k} \quad (19)$$

where $\tilde{c} = c_2 - \varepsilon + \sum_k 2^{k-1}$ encapsulates the aggregated scalar offsets and M is the number of slack qubits.

Substituting C_{slack} into the penalty expansion $(A + B + C_{slack})^2$ drastically alters the physical requirements. We decompose the resulting Hamiltonian $H_{P_{slack}}$ into its k -local sub-components:

- **0-local (Identity terms):**

$$H_{slack}^{(0)} = \lambda \left[\sum_u h_u^2 + \sum_{u<v} J_{uv}^2 + \tilde{c}^2 + \sum_k (2^{k-1})^2 \right] I_{tot} \quad (20)$$

- **1-local (Linear terms):**

$$H_{slack}^{(1)} = 2\lambda \sum_u \left[\sum_{v \neq u} h_v J_{uv} + \tilde{c} h_u \right] Z_u - 2\lambda \tilde{c} \sum_k 2^{k-1} Z_{s_k} \quad (21)$$

- **2-local (Quadratic terms):**

$$H_{slack}^{(2)} = 2\lambda \sum_{u<v} \left[h_u h_v + \tilde{c} J_{uv} + \sum_{w \neq u,v} J_{uw} J_{vw} \right] Z_u Z_v + 2\lambda \sum_{k<l} 2^{k-1} 2^{l-1} Z_{s_k} Z_{s_l} - 2\lambda \sum_{u,k} h_u 2^{k-1} Z_u Z_{s_k} \quad (22)$$

- **3-local (Cubic terms):**

$$H_{slack}^{(3)} = 2\lambda \sum_{u < v < w} (h_u J_{vw} + h_v J_{uw} + h_w J_{uv}) Z_u Z_v Z_w - 2\lambda \sum_{u < v, k} J_{uv} 2^{k-1} Z_u Z_v Z_{s_k} \quad (23)$$

- **4-local (Quartic terms):**

$$H_{slack}^{(4)} = 2\lambda \sum_{u < v < w < x} (J_{uv} J_{wx} + J_{uw} J_{vx} + J_{ux} J_{vw}) Z_u Z_v Z_w Z_x \quad (24)$$

Crucially, the $H_{slack}^{(3)}$ component reveals that every non-zero edge J_{uv} in the problem graph now interacts with *every* qubit in the slack register. This generates a massive proliferation of 3-local terms scaling as $\mathcal{O}(|E| \cdot M)$, where $|E|$ is the number of edges and M is the number of slack variables.

Additional tables

Table 1: Hypervolume (HV) Metrics Summary (Median \pm IQR) - Slack vs Hess ($n = 10$)

n	ρ	p	Slack-Grid		Slack-Iterative		Hess-Grid		Hess-Iterative	
			App	Ex	App	Ex	App	Ex	App	Ex
10	-0.7	0.2	1.00 \pm 0.00	0.99 \pm 0.01	1.00 \pm 0.00					
10	-0.7	1.0	1.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.00	0.99 \pm 0.01	0.99 \pm 0.02	1.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.00	0.99 \pm 0.03	0.99 \pm 0.02
10	0.0	0.2	1.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.01	1.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.01	0.99 \pm 0.01
10	0.0	1.0	1.00 \pm 0.01	1.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.03	0.99 \pm 0.02	1.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.00	0.98 \pm 0.03	0.98 \pm 0.03
10	0.7	0.2	1.00 \pm 0.00	0.98 \pm 0.02	1.00 \pm 0.01					
10	0.7	1.0	1.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.00	0.98 \pm 0.03	0.98 \pm 0.04	1.00 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.00	0.97 \pm 0.06	0.98 \pm 0.05

Table 2: Spacing Metrics Summary (Median \pm IQR) - Slack vs Hess ($n = 10$)

n	ρ	p	Slack-Grid		Slack-Iterative		Hess-Grid		Hess-Iterative	
			App	Ex	App	Ex	App	Ex	App	Ex
10	-0.7	0.2	19.31 \pm 0.00	19.31 \pm 0.00	19.31 \pm 0.00	19.31 \pm 0.50	19.31 \pm 0.00	19.31 \pm 0.00	19.31 \pm 2.72	19.31 \pm 0.00
10	-0.7	1.0	38.34 \pm 1.57	38.34 \pm 1.52	41.42 \pm 9.12	40.36 \pm 6.45	38.34 \pm 2.35	38.34 \pm 1.98	38.78 \pm 6.53	44.23 \pm 8.24
10	0.0	0.2	4.95 \pm 0.00	4.95 \pm 0.00	4.95 \pm 0.06	4.95 \pm 2.50	4.95 \pm 0.00	4.95 \pm 0.00	4.95 \pm 2.76	5.29 \pm 2.48
10	0.0	1.0	62.09 \pm 11.92	62.09 \pm 3.50	51.66 \pm 7.33	51.66 \pm 10.30	62.09 \pm 0.00	62.09 \pm 2.56	48.34 \pm 15.06	35.14 \pm 20.38
10	0.7	0.2	5.42 \pm 0.03	5.42 \pm 0.05	5.42 \pm 0.12	5.42 \pm 0.13	5.42 \pm 0.00	5.42 \pm 0.00	4.77 \pm 1.51	5.42 \pm 0.40
10	0.7	1.0	34.04 \pm 0.66	34.04 \pm 0.00	37.13 \pm 6.12	36.91 \pm 7.89	34.04 \pm 0.90	34.04 \pm 1.27	36.44 \pm 13.90	37.20 \pm 9.79

Table 3: Spacing Metrics Summary (Median \pm IQR) - Hess Methods ($n = 15$)

n	ρ	p	Hess-Grid		Hess-Iterative	
			App	Ex	App	Ex
15	-0.7	0.2	13.38\pm2.96	13.87 \pm 3.45	21.40 \pm 7.09	19.31 \pm 5.08
15	-0.7	1.0	28.67\pm8.32	31.65 \pm 8.89	42.57 \pm 14.32	58.74 \pm 15.16
15	0.0	0.2	14.25 \pm 5.29	13.98\pm4.08	21.70 \pm 7.83	21.89 \pm 7.82
15	0.0	1.0	51.03 \pm 23.88	45.09\pm17.44	66.61 \pm 47.15	61.28 \pm 58.18
15	0.7	0.2	5.02 \pm 15.04	3.38\pm13.10	10.97 \pm 19.53	25.98 \pm 18.64
15	0.7	1.0	34.32 \pm 13.65	32.25 \pm 21.85	0.00\pm24.90	0.00\pm18.29

Algorithm 1 Constrained QUBO via QAOA (Regular Grid)

- 1: **Initialization:**
- 2: $x_0 \leftarrow \arg \min_x x^\top Q_1 x$ ▷ Single objective QAOA
- 3: $\varepsilon_0 \leftarrow x_0^\top Q_2 x_0$
- 4: $x' \leftarrow \arg \min_x x^\top Q_2 x$ ▷ Single objective QAOA
- 5: $\varepsilon_{n_{\text{grid}}-1} \leftarrow x'^\top Q_2 x'$
- 6: Construct target grid $G = [\varepsilon_0, \varepsilon_1, \dots, \varepsilon_{n_{\text{grid}}-1}]$
- 7: Initialize Pareto set archive: $\mathcal{P} \leftarrow \{x_0, x'\}$
- 8: Initialize parameters $\theta_{\text{init}}, \beta_{\text{init}}, \gamma_{\text{init}}$
- 9: **for each** $\varepsilon_i \in G$ **do** ▷ Can be parallelized
- 10: Map primary objective: $x^\top Q_1 x \rightarrow H_1$
- 11: Construct penalty Hamiltonian:

$$H_{\text{penalty}}(\lambda_i, \varepsilon_i) = \lambda_i \left(\sum_{k=0}^4 H_{\text{penalty}}^{(k)}(\varepsilon_i) \right)$$

- 12: Define exact cost: $H_P = H_1 + H_{\text{penalty}}$
- 13: Define approximated Hamiltonian:

$$H_{P_{\text{approx}}}(\lambda_i, \varepsilon_i, \theta) = H_1 + \lambda_i \left(\sum_{k=0}^2 H_P^{(k)}(\varepsilon_i) + \hat{H}_2(\theta) \right)$$

- 14: Prepare QAOA state:

$$|\psi(\theta, \beta, \gamma)\rangle = \prod_{q=1}^p e^{-i\beta_q H_M} e^{-i\gamma_q H_{P_{\text{approx}}}} |+\rangle^{\otimes n}$$

- 15: Classically optimize parameters starting from $\theta_{\text{init}}, \beta_{\text{init}}, \gamma_{\text{init}}$:

$$\theta^*, \beta^*, \gamma^* \leftarrow \arg \min_{\theta, \beta, \gamma} \langle \psi(\theta, \beta, \gamma) | H_{P_{\text{ineq}}} | \psi(\theta, \beta, \gamma) \rangle$$

- 16: Update warm-start parameters: $\theta_{\text{init}} \leftarrow \theta^*, \beta_{\text{init}} \leftarrow \beta^*, \gamma_{\text{init}} \leftarrow \gamma^*$
- 17: Extract optimal bit-string x_i from optimized state
- 18: Update Pareto set: $\mathcal{P} \leftarrow \mathcal{P} \cup \{x_i\}$ ▷ Non-dominated sorting to keep only non-dominated solutions
- 19: **end for**
- 20: **return** Pareto set of bit-strings \mathcal{P}

Algorithm 2 Constrained QUBO via QAOA (Iterative Update)

- 1: **Initialization:**
- 2: $x_0 \leftarrow \arg \min_x x^\top Q_1 x$ ▷ Single objective QAOA
- 3: $\varepsilon_0 \leftarrow x_0^\top Q_2 x_0$
- 4: $x' \leftarrow \arg \min_x x^\top Q_2 x$ ▷ Single objective QAOA
- 5: $\varepsilon_{\text{target}} \leftarrow x'^\top Q_2 x'$
- 6: $i \leftarrow 0$
- 7: Initialize Pareto set archive: $\mathcal{P} \leftarrow \{x_0, x'\}$
- 8: Initialize parameters $\theta_{\text{init}}, \beta_{\text{init}}, \gamma_{\text{init}}$
- 9: **while** $\varepsilon_i \not\approx \varepsilon_{\text{target}}$ **do**
- 10: Map primary objective: $x^\top Q_1 x \rightarrow H_1$
- 11: Construct penalty Hamiltonian:

$$H_{\text{penalty}}(\lambda_i, \varepsilon_i) = \lambda_i \left(\sum_{k=0}^4 H_{\text{penalty}}^{(k)}(\varepsilon_i) \right)$$

- 12: Define exact cost: $H_P = H_1 + H'$
- 13: Define approximated Hamiltonian:

$$H_{P_{\text{approx}}}(\lambda_i, \varepsilon_i, \theta) = H_1 + \lambda_i \left(\sum_{k=0}^2 H_{\text{penalty}}^{(k)}(\varepsilon_i) + \hat{H}_2(\theta) \right)$$

- 14: Prepare QAOA state:

$$|\psi(\theta, \beta, \gamma)\rangle = \prod_{q=1}^p e^{-i\beta_q H_M} e^{-i\gamma_q H_{P_{\text{approx}}}} |+\rangle^{\otimes n}$$

- 15: Classically optimize parameters starting from $\theta_{\text{init}}, \beta_{\text{init}}, \gamma_{\text{init}}$:

$$\theta^*, \beta^*, \gamma^* \leftarrow \arg \min_{\theta, \beta, \gamma} \langle \psi(\theta, \beta, \gamma) | H_{P_{\text{ineq}}} | \psi(\theta, \beta, \gamma) \rangle$$

- 16: Update warm-start parameters: $\theta_{\text{init}} \leftarrow \theta^*, \beta_{\text{init}} \leftarrow \beta^*, \gamma_{\text{init}} \leftarrow \gamma^*$
- 17: Extract optimal bit-string x_{i+1} from optimized state
- 18: Update constraint limit: $\varepsilon_{i+1} \leftarrow x_{i+1}^\top Q_2 x_{i+1}$
- 19: Update Pareto set: $\mathcal{P} \leftarrow \mathcal{P} \cup \{x_{i+1}\}$ ▷ Non-dominated sorting to keep only non-dominated solutions
- 20: $i \leftarrow i + 1$
- 21: **end while**
- 22: **return** Pareto set of bit-strings \mathcal{P}